

years. They can be downloaded freely from the Internet. One of these datasets is the LiveLab dataset, which consists of mobile logs of 100 volunteers over the 14-month period. The dataset consists of fifteen different SQL tables. It has been studied in more than 278 scientific papers according to Google Scholar. Different hidden information has been extracted from it. Another online available dataset is in which has been cited in 342 papers. 30 volunteers participated to collect it. It focused on the accelerometer sensor. It has been extended in and obtained another 130 citations. They extended it by more instances. However, they did not add more sensors. Another example of a dataset that has been collected is in. This dataset focused on the Wi-Fi module in the smartphone, accelerometer, and gyroscope. Moreover, smartwatch data has been also recorded. A final example is the massive dataset, which consists of life-logged data of 35 users over two months. It recorded all smartphone activities of the users. This dataset obtained approximately 100 citations. A common feature of all of these datasets is that they did not record any of the users' content or any private data. In other words, the data collected are treated as normal data from smartphone users. With more than a thousand paper published with different extracted information from these datasets of nonprivate contents and data, it is obvious how this nonprivate data led to

the extraction of massive information that can track and identify users' activities.

Conclusion. Within the framework of this article, an information system for collecting and processing data from touch sensors of mobile devices is considered. The system allows you to implement the above-mentioned functions and management through mobile applications and cloud services.

The internet connection opens up new opportunities for companies, governments, and consumers with a wide range of everyday devices - from fitness bracelets to industrial equipment. In addition to this feature, there are also new issues such as performance, data privacy, and security issues – all of which should be kept in mind.

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ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE WELL FUND AT THE WEST KAZAKHSTAN FIELD

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Abstract

The efficiency of the operation of the oil well fund is analyzed, compared with the design indicators and the reasons for the discrepancy are identified.

The field was put into development in 1980, based on trial operation projects. Drilling of the deposit was carried out according to the pilot operation project.

In 2005, LLP "CTI" "RD "Kazmunaygas" recalculated the reserves of oil and dissolved gas.

Keywords: well, field, object, development, producing wells.

The newly calculated and approved initial balance sheet and recoverable oil reserves of the Republic of Kazakhstan are;

in the category B + C1 – 6287.9/ 2957 thousand tons, stocks increased by 18 and 49%.

Including:

- for the I– th object – 4587.9 thousand tons. geological, 2294 thousand tons. recoverable:

- for the II–th object - 1,700 thousand tons. geological, 663 thousand tons. recoverable:

Initial oil reserves for the field in category C2 – 959.5 / 429.3 thousand tons. increased by 78 and 141%.

In 2006, the II – development option was adopted for implementation, which provides for drilling and commissioning of 12 production wells and the transfer of 2 wells from the first facility to the second facility. The maximum fund of producing wells is 38.

Dynamics of the main indicators of development for the Dosmukhambetovskoye field

Analysis of the well fund for the Dosmukhambetovskoye field

Name	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
Operational fund	28	30	33	36	38	38
Current Fund	28	30	33	36	37	36
in inactivity					1	2
Observational	1	1	1	1	1	1
Liquidated	1	1	1	1	1	1
Fountain wells		1	2	2	1	1

Distribution of the current fund by oil debits

Field	Action. Fund	Oil flow rates, t/day				
		from 0 to 5	from 5 to 10	from 10 to 15	from 15 to 20	more than 20
Dosmukhambetovskoe	36	15	15	4	2	

Distribution of the current fund by water content

Field	Action. Fund	Water cut, 0					
		Up to 30%	30 - 50%	50 - 70%	70 - 90%	90 - 95%	more than 95%
Dosmukhambetovskoe	36	7	9	5	10	3	2

Initial recoverable reserves in category B+C1 - 3438 thousand tons, changed by 481 thousand tons, KIN - by 7.7%, recoverable oil reserves increased by 16.3%. The initial reservoir pressure is 23.4 MPa.

The current reservoir pressure is 18.0 – 22.0 MPa.

The average pressure at the faces of producing wells is 17.0-20.5 MPa.

As of 1.01.13, 40 wells were drilled; 36 wells were in operation, 2 wells were inactive, 1 observation well, 1 well was liquidated.

From the existing fund, 1 well is operated by the fountain method, 2 wells are UESN, 25 - EVN, 7 - SHGN.

In 2012, 75,939 thousand tons of oil, 3,568 million m³ of gas and 225,761 thousand tons of liquid were produced. The average annual gas factor is 47 m³/ton. The average annual water content is 66%, against the design 82%. The average flow rate of one well for oil is 6.0 tons /day, against the design 6.4 tons / day, for liquid – 17.9 tons / day, against the design 36.3 tons / day.

When comparing the actual indicators with the design, the annual oil production is 10.0 thousand tons lower, the total oil production is at the level of the design values, the average annual water content is 16% lower, respectively, there is a large lag in liquid production.

I – object (VIII1, VIII2, VIII3, VIII4). The facility has been under development since 1980. According to the type of natural reservoir, the deposit is stratified, arched, tectonically shielded.

The initial reservoir pressure is 24.0 MPa. The current reservoir pressure is 20.8 MPa. The saturation pressure is 4.8 MPa.

Geological reserves in category B +C1 for the I–object – 4588 thousand tons, recoverable - 2729 thousand tons. Since the beginning of development,

2118,977 thousand tons, 67,702 million m³ of gas and 6450,3 thousand tons of water have been extracted. The depletion of reserves is 78%, against the design – 90.5%. The rate of selection from the initial recoverable reserves for the facility is 8.0%.

The coefficient of oil recovery is 0.452, against the project - 0.45.

As of 1.01.13, 32 wells have been drilled, including 28 existing wells. 2 wells are inactive, 1 observation well, 1 well has been liquidated.

From the existing fund, one well works in a fountain way, 20 sle- EVN, 2 sle - ESN, 5 sle –SHGN.

In 2012, 57.11 thousand tons of oil, 2.34 million m³ of gas and 124.463 thousand tons of water were produced.

The average annual water content is 69%, against the project – 92%. The average annual gas factor is 41 m³/ton. The average flow rate of one well for oil is 5.3 tons/day, against the design 4.9 tons / day, for liquid - 18 tons /day. against the project 42.5 tons / day

Actual development values: average daily flow rate of 1 well for oil, KIN, oil production since the beginning of development at the level of design values.

The actual average annual water content is lower by 18%, respectively, the production of liquid is much lower than the design.

II – object (IX1 - XIV Middle Jurassic horizons). II – the facility has been under development since 1980. According to the type of natural reservoir, the deposit is stratified, arched, tectonically shielded. The initial reservoir pressure is 23.7 - 27.9 MPa. The current reservoir pressure is 21.9 – 26.8 MPa. The saturation pressure is 7.2 MPa.

The geological reserves of the facility are 1,700 thousand tons, recoverable reserves are 712 thousand tons. residual oil reserves from recoverable reserves of 475,154 thousand tons.

Oil recovery coefficient - 0.12, with the design - 0.18.

As of 1.01.13, 8 wells were drilled; including 8 operating wells. One well works in a fountain way, 4 sle- EVN, 3 sle –SHGN.

In 2012, 24,403 thousand tons of oil, 8,847 million m³ of gas and 441,068 thousand tons of liquid were produced.

The average annual water content is 51%, against the project – 32%. The average annual gas factor is 62 m³/ton. The average flow rate of one well for oil is 8.7 tons/day, against the design 10.6 tons / day, for liquid - 18 tons /day. against the project 16.1 tons / day.

When comparing the design indicators with the actual ones, there is a lag in oil and liquid production.

The reason for the backlog is the discrepancy between the existing well stock and the projected one.

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